

Chest Pain, Fever, and SVC Syndrome After Bronchoscopy

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ABSTRACT

The incidence of Mediastinitis after an EBUS procedure has been reported only in 7 cases out of 7345 in a nationwide study in 2013. We present a 61-year-old patient with not only Mediastinitis but with further complications of SVC syndrome after EBUS 1 month ago.

Keywords: Chest Pain; Fever; SVC Syndrome

BACKGROUND

A 61-year-old female presented with chest pain, dyspnea, and progressive swelling of her right upper extremity and right-sided neck veins. She was admitted to ICU for septic shock and was intubated. A month prior patient had a CT scan of the Chest (**Figure 1**), which showed an upper lobe cavitory lesion. Subsequently underwent an uneventful bronchoscopy with transbronchial lung biopsies of the right upper lobe cavitory lesion and endobronchial ultrasound (EBUS) guided aspiration of mediastinal lymph nodes. Pathology revealed necrotizing granulomas, and microbiology grew *Aspergillus* species.

Due to the patient's chest pain and dyspnea on presentation, repeat CT chest (**Figure 2**) revealed a new 6 cm necrotic paratracheal collection severely compressing the superior vena cava (SVC). Cultures from the collection grew *Actinomyces Odontolyticus*. Following antibiotic therapy and percutaneous drainage, the patient clinically improved, and SVC compression resolved.

The overall complication rate of EBUS with transbronchial biopsy performed on 7345 cases was 1.23%, with hemorrhage being the most frequent complication. Infectious complications developed in only 14 cases (0.19%) of those 7 cases were Mediastinitis.^[1]

SVC which generally associated with Malignancy in 60% of patients and Non-malignant conditions in 40% of patients, of which the majority is associated with intravascular devices. Of the benign causes, Mediastinitis only accounted for 8%.^[2-3]

Figure 1: CT chest prior to bronchoscopy demonstrating upper lobe cavitary lesion and mediastinal lymph nodes.

Figure 2: CT chest on presentation showing a new mediastinal mass (red arrow) and severe narrowing of SVC (green arrow)

CONCLUSION

Clinicians must be aware of Mediastinitis as a rare but severe complication of a commonly performed EBUS procedure.

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